

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

O'zbekistonda kreativ iqtisodiyotni qo'llash istiqbollari: 2025-2030 uchun imkoniyatlar va ustuvor yo'nalishlar

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Abstract. The topic of developing the creative economy in Uzbekistan has become a very active agenda in recent years within the framework of legal, institutional and international cooperation. This literature review summarizes the sources of normative and legal acts, international reports and national initiatives (Creative Park, incubator, IT ecosystem) that are the basis for the article, and serves to show their main ideas, strengths and limitations. It thereby reveals the evidence on which conclusions about the prospects of the creative economy in Uzbekistan are based.

Keywords: creative economy, IT park, Creative park, IT ecosystem, incubator

Anotatsiya. O'zbekistonda kreativ iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish mavzusi so'nggi yillarda huquqiy, institutsional va xalqaro hamkorlik doirasida ancha faol kun tartibiga chiqdi. Mazkur adabiyotlar sharhi maqolada tayanch bo'lgan normativ-huquqiy hujjatlar, xalqaro hisobotlar hamda milliy tashabbuslar (Creative Park, inkubator, IT ekotizimi) haqidagi manbalarni jamlab, ularning asosiy g'oyalari, kuchli tomoni va cheklovlarini ko'rsatishga xizmat qiladi. Shu orqali kreativ iqtisodiyotning O'zbekistondagi istiqbollari bo'yicha xulosalar qanday dalillarga tayanganini ochib beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: kreativ iqtisodiyot, IT park, Kreativ park, IT ekotizimi, incubator

Kirish

Kreativ iqtisodiyot — bu g'oya, ijodiy mehnat va intellektual kapitalga tayanib qiymat yaratuvchi tarmoqlar majmui: dizayn, moda, kino, musiqa, nashriyot, reklama, IT va o'yinlar (game development), animatsiya, hunarmandchilik, madaniy merosga bog'liq xizmatlar va boshqalar. Bunday tarmoqlar "nomoddiy" ko'ringani bilan iqtisodiy natijasi juda moddiy: bandlik, xizmatlar eksporti, turizm daromadlari, brend qiymati, shaharlar jozibadorligi, innovatsiya va mahsulot raqobatbardoshligi.

So'nggi yillarda O'zbekistonda bu yo'nalish institutsional darajada kun tartibiga chiqdi: 2024-yil 3-oktabrda "Kreativ iqtisodiyot to'g'risida"gi qonun qabul qilinib, 2024-yil 4-oktabrdan kuchga kirgani qayd etilgan. Bu, kreativ tarmoqlarni alohida siyosat obyekti sifatida ko'rish va ularga xizmat qiladigan infratuzilma hamda moliyalashtirish mexanizmlarini tizimli qurish uchun muhim huquqiy poydevor demakdir.

Adabiyotlar sharxi

Kreativ iqtisodiyot bo'yicha eng ko'p uchraydigan muammo — **ta'riflarning turlicha bo'lishi** va natijada statistik solishtirishning qiyinlashishidir. UNCTAD'ning *Creative Economy Outlook 2024* hisobotida kreativ iqtisodiyotning mamlakatlar bo'yicha YAIM va bandlikdagi ulushi keng diapazonda ekanligi, ammo ma'lumotlar bir-biriga to'liq taqqoslanmasligi (turli ta'riflar, turli o'lchovlar va turli yil kesimi) qayd etiladi.

Maqoladagi eng asosiy tayanch manba — 2024-yil 3-oktabrda qabul qilingan "Kreativ iqtisodiyot to'g'risida"gi Qonun (O'RQ-970).

Metodologiya

Ushbu tadqiqotda mavzu bo'yicha muhim ma'lumotlarni berish uchun tarixiy, induktiv va deduktiv usullardan foydalanildi.

Tahlil va natijalar: Nega aynan O'zbekiston uchun kreativ iqtisodiyot istiqbolli?

O'zbekistonning kreativ iqtisodiyotga tayanchi bo'ladigan uchta kuchli omili bor:

1. Madaniy kapital va meros: tarixiy shaharlar, hunarmandchilik maktablari, milliy naqsh, to'qimachilik va zargarlik an'analari — bularning barchasi mahsulot dizayni, suvenir, interyer, moda, turizm tajribasi va kontent (film/multimedia) uchun "xomashyo" vazifasini bajaradi.

2. Raqamli xizmatlar orqali eksport imkoniyati: kreativ xizmatlar (dizayn, animatsiya, o'yinlar, multimedia, dasturiy mahsulot) geografiyaga kamroq bog'liq, ya'ni "masofadan" turib ham eksport qilinadi.

3. Yoshlar resursi: kreativ kasblar, odatda, yoshlar uchun tez o'zlashtiriladigan, mustaqil daromad topishga imkon beradigan yo'nalishlar bo'lib, O'zbekistonda aynan yoshlar bandligini kengaytirish siyosati bilan uyg'unlashadi.

Siyosiy-institutsional baza: qonun, parklar va inkubatsiya

O'zbekistonda kreativ iqtisodiyotning "ekotizimi" shakllanishi bir nechta parallel yo'nalishda ketmoqda:

1) Maqsadli ko'rsatkich: YAIMda ulushni oshirish

IT Park va hamkorlarining Creative Incubator ochilishiga bag'ishlangan rasmiy xabarida 2024-yil 3-oktabrdagi Kreativ iqtisodiyot haqidagi qonun ijrosi doirasida kreativ industriyalarning YAIMga hissasini **2030-yilgacha 5% ga yetkazish** maqsadi tilga olingan. Bu ko'rsatkich — kreativ iqtisodiyotni "madaniyat" gina emas, balki iqtisodiy diversifikatsiya va eksportning real drayveri sifatida ko'rish belgisi.

2) Hududiy infratuzilma: Creative Parklar

Toshkentdagi Yoshlar ijod saroyida "model Creative Park" tashkil etilib, keyin barcha hududlarda shunday markazlarni barpo etish rejalari haqida xabar berilgan. Muhimi, park rezidentlari uchun preferensial soliq rejimi ko'zda tutilgani qayd etiladi (jumladan, JShDS va ijtimoiy soliq bo'yicha 50% chegirma, aylanmadan soliq rejimi).

3) "Soft" infratuzilma: inkubator, ta'lim va biznes ko'nikmalari

Creative Incubator loyihasi dizayner, animator, dasturchi, tadbirkor va boshqa kreativ mutaxassislar uchun ta'lim, master-klass, pitch va mentorlik kabi amaliy resurslar berishini ta'kidlaydi.

O'zbekistonda eng tez o'sishi mumkin bo'lgan kreativ yo'nalishlar

UNCTADning Creative Economy Outlook 2024 hujjatida O'zbekiston eksport bo'yicha e'tibor qaratayotgan kreativ mahsulot va xizmatlar sifatida quyidagilar sanaladi:

dasturiy ta'minot, madaniy-tarixiy meros va hunarmandchilik, zargarlik, to'qimachilik, kinematografiya. Bu ro'yxat O'zbekiston uchun tabiiy "prioritet portfel" bo'lib, ularni qiymat zanjiri nuqtayi nazaridan shunday kuchaytirish mumkin:

1) Raqamli kreativ xizmatlar: dizayn-animatsiya-o'yinlar-multimedia

Raqamli yo'nalishning ustunligi — eksportga chiqish tezligi va nisbatan kam kapital talab qilishi. 2025-yilning dastlabki 7 oyida IT Parkka qo'shilgan eksportga yo'naltirilgan yangi kompaniyalar tarkibida game development bilan shug'ullanuvchilar ham borligi (21 ta) qayd etilgan, shuningdek IT Park a'zolari xizmatlarni 90 dan ortiq mamlakatga eksport qilayotgani aytiladi.

2) Hunarmandchilik va madaniy meros: "storytelling" + dizayn + turizm

Hunarmandchilikni faqat suvenir sifatida emas, balki: dizayn mahsuloti (interyer, dekor, moda aksessuarlari), turizm tajribasi (workshop, "ustaxonaga sayohat festival), premium sovg'a bozoriga mos brendli kolleksiya sifatida qayta qadoqlash zarur. Bunda autentiklik va sifat standarti muhim: sertifikatlash, geografik ko'rsatkichlar, brend himoyasi, qadoqlash, logistika va onlayn savdo (cross-border e-commerce) kabi bo'g'inlar qo'shilsa, bitta buyumning qo'shilgan qiymati bir necha barobar oshadi.

3) Moda va tekstil: "xomashyo"dan "brend"ga

To'qimachilik O'zbekistonda an'anaviy kuchli tarmoq. Kreativ iqtisodiyot nuqtayi nazaridan esa asosiy vazifa — "ishlab chiqarish"dan "brend va dizayn"ga ko'tarilish: dizaynerlar bilan kapsula-kolleksiyalar, mahalliy naqsh va mato identifikatsiyasi, elektron tijorat orqali eksport, xalqaro ko'rgazmalar va "Made in Uzbekistan" brendi ostida targ'ibot.

4) Kino, serial, animatsiya va media

UNCTAD hujjatida O'zbekiston kinematografiyani ham kreativ eksport prioritetlaridan biri sifatida ko'rsatadi. Bu yo'nalishda iqtisodiy samaradorlik "bitta film"dan ko'ra kengroq: post-prodakshn (montaj, VFX), animatsiya va motion design, musiqiy mahsulot, lokatsiya turizmi (film tourism), intellektual mulkdan licenziya va merchandising daromadlari.

Asosiy muammolar: "g'oya"dan "barqaror biznes"ga o'tishdagi to'siqlar

Kreativ sektorda odatda quyidagi iqtisodiy muammolar uchraydi: norasmiy bandlik, daromadning mavsumiyligi, moliyalashtirishga kirish qiyinligi, intellektual mulk himoyasi va adolatli haq to'lash mexanizmlarining zaifligi.

2025-2030 uchun amaliy "yo'l xaritasi" taklifi

Quyidagi yondashuv O'zbekistonda kreativ iqtisodiyotning tez o'sishini ta'minlaydi:

1) Statistika va "o'lchash" tizimi: nimani rivojlantirayotganimizni aniq bilish

- Kreativ tarmoqlar tasnifini milliy statistika bilan uyg'unlashtirish (subsektorlar kesimida).
- Bandlik, eksport, daromad, startaplar, festival/event iqtisodiyoti kabi KPIlarni muntazam yuritish.

UNCTADning O'zbekiston bo'yicha harakat rejasi ishlab chiqishga qaratilgan loyihasi ham aynan data va capacity buildingga urg'u berishini ko'rsatadi.

2) Moliyalashtirish: grant + inkubatsiya + bozorga chiqish

- Mikrograntlar (prototip, kolleksiya, pilot epizod, demo o'yin).
- Inkubatsiya orqali investor/potensial xaridor bilan bog'lash.
- Kreativ bizneslar uchun kredit kafolatlari va "revenue-based"(daromadga bog'langan) moliyalashtirish mexanizmlarini sinovdan o'tkazish.

3) Creative Park va inkubatorlarni "hududiy klaster"ga aylantirish

Creative Parklar nafaqat bino, balki xizmatlar to'plami bo'lishi kerak: studiyalar, uskunalar, yuridik/IP klinikalari, eksport bo'yicha maslahat, marketplace, foto/video kontent laboratoriyalari. Preferensial soliq rejimi esa rezidentlar uchun "xavfni kamaytiruvchi"omil bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

4) Eksport strategiyasi: "raqamli xizmatlar + madaniy mahsulotlar"

UNCTAD hujjatida O'zbekistonda eksportni rag'batlantirish bo'yicha milliy choralar va 2018-yilda "Made in Uzbekistan"brendi ostida ko'rgazmalar orqali targ'ibot tajribasi tilga olinadi. Bu tajribani kuchaytirish uchun: dizayn/multimedia/game dev bo'yicha "export studio"lar, xalqaro platformalarda (marketplace) savdo ko'nikmalari, turizm bilan bog'langan kreativ mahsulot paketlari (festival + craft + gastro + retail) kerak.

5) Intellektual mulk va shaffof shartnomalar

Kreativ sektorda "adolatli bozor"ning asosi — IP. WIPOning 2024-yil oktabrida Toshkentdagi Kreativ iqtisodiyot konferensiyasida ishtiroki ham intellektual mulk masalasi global kun tartibida ekanini ko'rsatadi. Amaliy choralar: mualliflik huquqi/brand/trademark bo'yicha arzon va tezkor maslahat xizmatlari, standart shartnoma shablonlari (dizayn buyurtmasi, video prodakshn, musiqiy licenziya), platformalarda monetizatsiya va huquqiy savodxonlik.

6) Raqamli infratuzilma: AI va data markazlar — kontent iqtisodiyotining tayanchi

Raqamli kreativ xizmatlar sifatli internet, data markazlar, hisoblash quvvatiga tayanadi. Reuters 2025-yil noyabrida Qoraqalpog'istonda AI va data-markaz loyihalari uchun soliqdan ozod zona yaratish tashabbusi haqida yozgan.

Xulosa

O'zbekistonda kreativ iqtisodiyot "qo'shimcha yo'nalish"emas, balki iqtisodiy diversifikatsiya, yoshlar bandligi, xizmatlar eksporti va milliy brendni kuchaytirishning real instrumentiga aylanmoqda.

Eng katta istiqbol — O'zbekistonning ikki ustunini birlashtirishda: madaniy meros (craft, dizayn, turizm) va raqamli kreativ xizmatlar (dizayn, animatsiya, o'yinlar, multimedia). Agar data, moliyalashtirish, IP va bozorga chiqish mexanizmlari izchil qurilsa, 2025-2030 yillarda kreativ iqtisodiyot O'zbekistonning eng tez o'suvchi, eksportbop va yoshlarni jalb qiluvchi tarmoqlaridan biriga aylanishi mumkin.

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